

HUMANISTIC APPROACH OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING AS A SECOND LANGUAGE WITH ANALYSIS ON INTRALINGUAL ERRORS

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Abstract:

'Writing' skill is very important for English learners. Most of the learners of English as a second language commit many errors during any kind of writing tasks. This study is an analysis on Intralingual errors on writing 'Tense Shift' in a paragraph via dictation (Simple Present Tense to be shifted into Simple Past Tense) written by level one students i.e. the first year students of Engineering and Technology, conducted at two colleges which are located in Coimbatore (District), Tamilnadu (State). This research suggests some of the possible reasons and explanations to avoid intralingual errors. The focus of the research is about the 'Humanistic Approach' of English Language Teaching and Learning as a second language and its classroom techniques, aiming at finding out the intralingual errors and its causes, categorizing and analysing the errors related to Pit Corder's (1974) theory of Error Analysis (EA), showing some correction techniques and role of planning, error versus mistake and also sheds light on implications for English Language Teaching – Learning and Testing.

Key Words: Writing; Intralingual Errors, Humanistic Approach, Error Analysis (EA), Correction Planning, Mistake, Implications & Teaching – Learning and Testing.

Introduction:

The study provides a detailed account of the development of the Humanistic approach of language teaching and learning as a second language and its techniques to be followed in the classroom. The subsequent sections will enable the reader to become better informed about the theory of language teaching from ancient roots to present-day trends i.e. from Grammar translation method to Humanistic approach with the four methods such as 1. The Silent Way 2. Community Language Learning 3. Suggestopaedia and 4. Total Physical Response which incorporates or reflects the philosophy of Humanistic approach. Sameway, the study identifies and classify the intralingual errors committed by the first year students' of Engineering and Technology (B.E/B.Tech) studying in the Coimbatore district.

The purpose of the thesis is to present a contemporary situation of second language learning and teaching, to identify major trends and issues, to show where these trends and issues have come from, and to illustrate ways - teachers can incorporate these ideas in their own teaching practice. On the other part, it outlines the errors made by the students' in learning a language and also the remedial measures to be undertaken. The thesis is intended for practicing teachers as well as future teachers.

The thesis is an outline map whereas the chapters state the role of English Education India and the World and the framework of the English Language Teaching-Learning and the need for communication skills among Engineering students.

The thesis traces the earlier and new trends of Language Teaching methods and approaches and also covers important features of second language teaching methods—grammar-translation, direct, The Textbook Method, The Reading Method, The Bilingual Method, The audiolingual, The Structural and situational approach, the Humanistic approach, the Silent Way, Suggestopedia, community language learning, Total Physical Response, and the communicative-Natural approach and Implications of the approaches are summarized.

Moreover, it deals with the changing role of the teacher to facilitator and the use of technology in language learning activities in particular to Engineering education and traces the Techniques, study aids followed in teaching a language in present scenario and technical education in Engineering and Technology colleges. Syllabus, text book, materials used, evaluation pattern were discussed. Professional Development goals and Strategies, teacher and student roles, the teaching/learning process, student-teacher and student-student interaction, dealing with feelings, view of language and culture, , means for evaluation, and response to student errors and remedies.

Three interrelated pedagogical elements—approach, design, and procedure—are basic in a discussion of language teaching. Thus, the thesis recommend that their views be taken into consideration when formulating the English curriculum and developing courses in Engineering colleges and Universities in the future. The English language programme for students of Engineering will motivate them only when they see the direct

benefits it brings to them. To equip teachers with the skills and competences needed for their new roles, it is necessary to have both quality education and professional development.

Whenever a man attempts to learn or acquire any language, he/she would definitely come across with some problem of errors. Therefore, making errors while learning a language are inevitable. Errors provide valuable insight into the process of learning a language. From 1950s to 1970s the study of errors has been roughly determined in three phases: Contrastive analysis, Error analysis and the theory of Interlanguage. However, by analysing the errors made by the language learners one could build up a picture of the features which cause problems while learning a language. Thus, the right perspective counter or remedial measures could be thought of and also be worked out to correct the learners' errors and get into the target language English as second language learning.

Methodology:

In the research, the primary step employed is 1. Self-designed survey questionnaire in choice-response task (totally - 300) for the level one students i.e. the first year students studying Engineering (B.E.) and Technology (B.Tech.) once after the immediate transformation of the higher secondary studies in school of rural and urban background which includes both the gender (boys and girls). A self-designed questionnaire for the first year students (150) from each college are randomly selected from five departments, which are located in Coimbatore (District) affiliated to Anna University of Technology, Coimbatore are selected for the research. 2. Self-designed survey questionnaire in choice-response task (totally - 20 members) for the members of faculty of English and (2 members) from each college working in various (10) Engineering and Technology colleges in Coimbatore (District) which assumed as a, b, c, d, e... is also employed for the research.

A self-designed survey questionnaire for the students is conducted in this study to gain a deeper understanding of students' interest in four language skills (Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing) and some of their expectations in language classroom etc., On the other, Self-designed survey questionnaire for the members of faculty of English is conducted in order to observe the kind of the approaches or the methodologies that they are ever interested to follow in their teaching etc., The main objective of the research which can also be called as the hypotheses for the data and interpretation is an analysis on 'Intralingual' Errors. The three steps of Error Analysis (EA) specified by Pit Corder's (1974) are followed:

- Collection of Sample Errors
- Identification of Errors
- Description of Errors

The first step is the collection of sample errors from the 300 test papers conducted on 'Tense shift' (Simple present tense into simple past tense given in the brackets in the form of paragraph via dictation). The purpose of the study is to find the difficulties of the students that they have in English language learning and which kind of errors' the students make in grammar. The duration of the language testing is of one hour and the students have to write the test in the classrooms. The writing task is of a paragraph in no less than 150 words. During the period of the test, there seems to be no instruction or suggestions from the teacher, neither could they discuss with their classmates nor referring any dictionaries.

With the help of the other English professors, the linguistic errors in the sample test papers have been found out and they are classified into seven types of grammatical errors. The errors will be counted by hand instead of machine or computer. The following is a paragraph that is given in the test paper.

'Tense Shift': The verbs in the text should all be in the past simple tense ('be' verbs, 'have' verbs, 'do' verbs). You have to find the verbs that are in the present tense and correct them.

Mrs. Julie is the richest woman in the city, but she is also a busybody. She always wanted to know what everybody is doing. When she needs something she rings a bell and a servant came. One day a truck stops in front of her house and the three men got out. They are carrying a large box. Mrs. Julie sees this and told her servant, John, to go and see what the men is doing. John goes out and spoke to the men but they don't tell him. When he came back Mrs. Julie is very angry with him. Next she sent Peter to find out. He didn't want to go at first and Mrs. Julie told him he is afraid. When he goes out the men ignored him when he said good morning. He tries again but this time the big man hit him in the stomach and he fell on the ground. Mrs. Julie sees all this and came on to the street. The men take her by the arms and put her in the box.

The second step is the identification of errors. The seven types of errors identified are stated below.

- Omission: missing grammatical forms while writing.
- Addition: adding grammatical forms where it is unnecessary.
- Fragment: leaving out punctuation marks wherever necessary such as capitals, comma, etc.,
- Lexis (selection of the words) – vocabulary
- Syntax (structure of the sentences) – grammar (i.e.) word order, subject verb agreement etc.,
- Simplification- word change (i.e) Tenses etc.,
- Interpretive - misunderstanding of a speaker's intention or meaning

The following is the sample of the student response in the test on 'Tense Shift'. Error Analysis is identified with different colours and italicised:

Mrs. Julie 1. *ad* - was being (is) the richest woman in the city, but she was (is) also a busybody. She always wanted to 1. *lexis* - no what everybody 1. *Omis* - ___ (is) doing. When she 1. *simp* - need (needs) something she 2. *ad* - was rang (rings) a bell and a servant came . One day a truck 2. *simp* -stop (stops) in front of her house and 2. *Omis* - ___ three men got out. They 3. *Omis* - ___ (are) carrying a large box. Mrs. Julie saw (sees) this and told her servant 1. *frag* ___ john ___ to go and see what the men 1. *Syn* - was (is) doing. John went (goes) out and spoke to the men but they 3. *simp* - don't told (don't) tell him. When he came back Mrs. Julie 3. *Omis* - ___ (is) very 2. *lexis* - hungry with him. Next she 2. *Syn* - _? _ 2. *frag* - peter to find out. He didn't want to go at first and Mrs. Julie told him he 3. *ad* was who (is) afraid. When he went (goes) out the men ignored him when he said good morning. He 3. *lexis* - tied (ties) again but this time the 1. *Interp* - pig man 2. *Interp* - pit him in the stomach and he fell on the 3. *Interp* - round. Mrs. Julie ___ saw ___ (sees) all this 3. *frag* ___ came on to the street. The men took (take) her by the arms and put 3. *Syn* - him in the box.

The third step is the description of the errors analysis.

1. Omission: The omission errors constituted 26.39% the highest percentage. For Example:

1. What everybody ___ (is) doing. 2. ___ three men got out 3. They ___ (are) carrying a large box

The first type of omission is the word (simple past tense) 'was' before the verb 'doing'

The correct sentence is: What everybody was doing.

The second type of omission is the omission of the definite Article 'the' before the count 'three' :

The correct sentence is: The three men got out

The third type of omission is the omission of the (simple past tense - plural) 'were' before the verb 'carrying'

The correct sentence is: They were carrying a large box

2. Addition: The addition errors constitute 20.68 % in this category.

1. Mrs. Julie was being (is) the richest woman 2. She was rang (rings) a bell

3. he was who (is) afraid

The first type of addition was the addition of 'being' with the (simple past tense) 'was'.

The correct sentence is: Mrs. Julie was (is) the richest woman.

The second type of addition was the addition of simple past tense 'was' with the already changed past tense 'rang'

The correct sentence is: she rang (rings) a bell

The third type of addition was the addition of 'wh'? question 'who' with the simple past tense 'was'

The correct sentence is: he was (is) afraid

3. Fragment: The sentence fragment second lowest errors constituting only 8.13 % of the total.

1. her servant ___ john ___ to go 2. peter to find out 3. this ___ came on to the street

The first type of fragment error is missing of punctuation mark (comma) ',' before and after the proper noun in the sentence.

The correct sentence is: her servant, John, to go

The second type of fragment error is missing of capital letter 'P' in the proper noun (name)

The correct sentence is: sent Peter to find out

The third type of fragment error is missing of conjunction 'and' which joins one part of the clause with one another clause to give the relative or complete meaning of the sentence.

The correct sentence is: this and came on to the street

4. Lexis (Selection of the Correct Word): The Lexis or the selections of word errors constitute 15.83% of the total errors.

1. She always wanted to no 2. Mrs. Julie was (is) very hungry 3. He tied (ties) again

The first type of lexis difficulty is the spelling error in a word. Some of the students have written 'no' instead of writing the correct word as 'know' in the sentence.

The correct sentence is: She always wanted to know

The second type of lexis difficulty is the same kind of spelling error as made in the first example. Students had written 'hungry' instead of writing 'angry'.

The correct sentence is: Mrs. Julie was (is) very angry

The third type of lexis difficulty is the error made in the bracket. Some of the students had written as 'tieds' in the bracket instead of the correct word simple present tense as 'tries'. So, while changing the present tense into past tense in the answer also they had written 'tied' as the past tense which gives the different meaning.

The correct sentence is: He tried (tries) again

5. Syntax (Structure of the sentence): This type of error constitutes 16.83 % of the total errors.

1. The men was (is) doing 2. Next she ___ 3. Put him in the box.

The first type of syntactic error is in Concord otherwise known as subject - verb agreement. In the sentence while changing into simple past tense 'were' (plural) to be written instead of 'was'.

The correct sentence is: the men were (is) doing

The second type of syntactic error is the missing of the verb 'sent' in the sentence. Without the verb the sentence will not give the complete meaning.

The correct sentence is: Next she sent

The third type of syntactic error occurred while writing the pronoun (Gender) as ‘him’ instead of ‘her’ in the sentence.

The correct sentence is: put her in the box.

6. Simplification: The simplification errors constitute 8.41% of the total errors.

1. She need (needs) something
2. Truck stop (stops) in front of her house
3. They don’t told (don’t) tell him

The first type of simplification error is omission of ‘ed’ in the word ‘need’ which make the sense of the past tense.

The correct sentence is: she needed (needs) something

The second type of simplification error is the rules of spelling (consonant ‘ p’ as ‘pp’) and omission of ‘ed’ in the word ‘stop’ to be as ‘stopped’ which make the past tense in a word.

The correct sentence is: truck stopped (stops) in front of her house

The third type of simplification error is ignorant of tenses. Instead to change ‘don’t’ as ‘didn’t’ or ‘did not’. Students had changed ‘tell’ into ‘told’ which had not given in the bracket to change into past tense.

The correct sentence is: they didn’t or did not (don’t) tell him

7. Interpretive Error: An Interpretive errors constituting only 3.70% of the total. This is the seventh common error.

1. The pig man.
2. Pit him in the stomach
3. On the round

The first type of interpretive error is the misinterpret of ‘big’ as ‘pig’

The correct sentence is: the big man

The second type of interpretive error is as the same misinterpretation as first example ‘hit’ as ‘pit’

The correct sentence is: hit him in the stomach

The third type of interpretive error is also the same misinterpret ‘ground’ as ‘round’

The correct sentence is: on the ground

Findings:

After counting the intralingual errors of 300 test papers by hand, what is discovered is that the English learners as a second language both from rural and urban background commit many errors. The errors made by the girls in each category (rural and urban) of both the colleges are comparatively less than those errors made by the boys. 701 intralingual errors have been found in the random sampling. The number of errors are listed in table which also present the errors in percentages.

Table 1: Overall Errors

S.No	Level	Name of the College (S)	Degree/Year	Classification of Errors	Total No. of Errors	Errors in %
1.	I Year	A & B	B.E, & B. Tech,	Omission	185	26.39087
				Addition	145	20.684736
				Fragment	57	8.1312411
				Lexis	111	15.834522
				Syntax	118	16.833096
				Simplification	59	8.4165478
				Interpretive	26	3.7089872
Total				701	100	

Figure 1: Errors in percentages

Conclusion:

Today the professional language teacher desires to follow various techniques in the language classroom and day- by- day trying to invent new strategies to be implemented in language teaching. Choosing techniques from each methods and approaches either from the old trends or the new approaches like Humanistic language teaching which they consider effective and applying it according to the learning context and objectives will

definitely make the teaching a very effective and a pleasant environment. A total of 701 errors were found and categorized into seven types of errors. The top seven common errors which are given as the keywords for the correction technique includes (1) Tense (2) Pronoun (3) Spelling and Punctuation (4) Verb (5) Subject-Verb agreement (6) linking devices/conjunctions and (7) Word choice. Overgeneralization, ignorance of rule restrictions, simplification is the major causes for the errors of learners. Errors in writing such as tenses, vocabulary are the most common and frequent types of errors that are committed by learners. Thus, it can be seen that error analysis have been used in second language learning as an effective research way. More writing tasks should be put in English testing in order to improve students' writing ability and teachers should be very cautious of teaching grammar efficiently and correctly and must take some measures to improve the students' ability of application of English grammar.

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